

*The first evidence-based altimetry for locating the lost
Eighth Wonder of the World: the Pink, Black and White
Terraces*

Rex Bunn

In the late nineteenth century, the greatest tourist attraction in the southern hemisphere were the Pink, Black and White Terraces, the lost Eighth Wonder of the World. British, European and American tourists bypassed the new Yellowstone on the new rail, to take ship across the Pacific to New Zealand. The Terraces' global fascination remains today.

It is axiomatic the Pink, Black and White Terraces cannot be found without accurate altimetry. This is due to a landform transformed by the 1886 Mt Tarawera and Rotomahana-Makariri eruptions and chronic erosion. Some 60 m of ejecta fell onto the area; burying the Terraces whose platforms lay 26 m and 30 m above the lake shore (Keam and Lloyd, 2016; Bunn, 2021). Compounding this is the virtual disappearance of the pre-1886 Lakes' Rotomahana and Makariri after the Mt Tarawera eruption; which extended from the Tarawera massif beneath the lakes, triggering further phreatic and hydrothermal eruptions. These deeply excavated the old lakes floors, depositing thick ejecta over the surrounding countryside. The new Lake Rotomahana is 10 times larger and 12 times deeper than the old, with its elevation ranging 33–39 meters above the old. Nearly all proximal landmarks were destroyed or buried in the 1886 eruptions.

Under these circumstances, establishing the latitude and longitude coordinates of proximal features like old Lake Rotomahana or the Pink, Black and White Terraces is insufficient to locate the features. Accurate horizontal location is impossible without pre-eruption survey data. Before 2016, none was known to exist. Even with such data, knowledge of a feature elevation is necessary to judge its depth today or assess station intervisibility. Altimetry becomes the spatial imperative for Terrace research and excavation. Drilling and excavation remain the

only ways to obtain in situ Terrace samples.

The first formal altimetry of Lake Rotomahana (1,088 ft) and of the Pink, Black and White Terraces was performed by Ferdinand Hochstetter (1829–1884) on his 1859 New Zealand expedition (Bunn & Nolden, 2018). A later estimate of 1,080 ft (329 m) published by S. P. (Percy) Smith (1840-1922) in 1887 (Smith, 1887); was likely a reiteration of Hochstetter’s figure, based on his Lake Tarawera record of 1,040 ft: as was Malfroy’s 1891 estimate. Malfroy however, anticipated the correct Rotomahana altitude of 303 MASL (Healy, 1975b). Smith, and others also recorded the descent of the Kaiwaka Stream as 40 ft (12 m), which is a key to our altimetry. In 1894, Smith reduced his Lake Rotomahana altitude to 1,013 ft (309 m), (Smith, 1894). Further measurements were precluded by the 1886 Mt Tarawera eruption.

Augustus Koch (1834–1901) was in charge of Hochstetter’s altimetry and equipped with a Kapeller Bourdon-type pressure gauge. His recorded altitudes were inaccurate for altimetry with such pressure gauge technology was in its infancy His gauge required calibration at sea level. Once the party left the coast, they were unable to calibrate it. “A great number of barometrical observations have afforded me the means of ascertaining the heights of a variety of mountains and plains in the interior, which I shall be able to calculate with accuracy by the aid of corresponding daily observations, taken in Auckland by Colonel Mould, who has kindly forwarded me a copy of his tables” (Hochstetter, 1859).

These early Bourdon gauges used crude linkages, had a lagged response, were prone to hysteresis and gave inconsistent readings. Readings also varied with temperature and humidity. Hochstetter addressed this by arranging observations at Auckland. On his return, he revised the readings against the Auckland data and reported a surface elevation for Lake Rotomahana of 1,088 ft (333 MASL). This is 30 m (9.9%) above the first present-day altimetry (Bunn and Nolden, 2018). Air pressure in these mountain areas of New Zealand differs from that at Auckland sea level. It alters continuously on the high central plateau. This kind of altimetry was superseded in 1928 by Paul Kollsmann’s (1900–1982) first aviation altimeter (Reynolds, 1953).

In previous papers the necessity for altimetry was demonstrated and the only evidence-based altimetry for old Lake Rotomahana and the Terraces developed (Bunn and Nolden, 2018). Contributing to this was the 1975 estimation by Rotorua geologist James Healy OBE (1910–1994), who examined the colonial literature on the relative elevations of Lakes’ Tarawera and Rotomahana and suggested a Lake Rotomahana elevation of 301 MASL (Healy, 1975b). Our 2014–2020 altimetry was based on his evidence, 1970 borehole coring reported by James Healy, colonial artwork and sixteen eyewitnesses (Bunn, 2020). We determined the Lake Rotomahana elevation was 303 MASL \pm 1–2 m between 1858–1886, consistent with Healy’s conclusion (Bunn & Nolden, 2018); close to Smith’s revised 1894 estimate and to Malfroy’s

1891 estimate (Healy, 1975b).

Other twenty-first century researchers ignored this body of empirical research in favour of Ron Keam's (R. F. Keam 1932–2019) admitted guess, i.e. that the Lake Rotomahana altitude was ≤ 292 MASL (Keam, 2016). Their 11–12 m error is significant when considering Terrace altitudes, sub-surface imaging, landmark intervisibility, elevation-profiling, drilling, core-sampling or excavation. Such research conclusions relying on Keam's guess are therefore nugatory. A Rotomahana altimetry based on hearsay without evidence, fails Christopher Hitchens's (1949–2011) razor: what can be asserted without evidence, can also be dismissed without evidence (Hitchens, 2008).

This first modern altimetry is strengthened with the recent addition of boreholes near Healy's 1970 borehole (Healy, 1975a). In 2013, the Bay of Plenty Regional Council (BOPRC) commissioned two boreholes on the true right bank of the Tarawera River entry flat. One of these, BN-1000134 (Bore No. 3), delivered a core containing 5 m of 1886 ejecta i.e. from 298–293 MASL (Tschrutter and White, 2014). This hole is located 20 m from the new river course, over the pre-1886 true right river bank in the river flat. Healy's 1970 hole lies nearby on the left bank. The river forms on the left side of the outlet today. Given the lake shoreline, the old river channel likely also lay to the left. In this area, the ground is 298 MASL. Lake Tarawera limnology has its surface area altering slowly with depth, due to its steep lake walls. Catchment and flow modelling in 2014 showed a river depth in the boreholes' area of 1–2 m (Bunn, 2014). Thus, the volumetric flow down the old and new (post-eruption) Tarawera Rivers was similar.

As Healy's borehole was considered to penetrate the old river bed at 291 MASL, and Tschrutter's borehole penetrated the old river bank at 293 MASL; it may be gauged the 1886 Tarawera River altitude here was at 291–293 MASL on eruption eve (Keir, 2016). Nairn reports "the Tarawera River flows across the Pokohu lava in a shallow, narrow (c. 10 m wide), low-gradient channel ... the pre-AD 1886 Lake Tarawera was c. 9 m lower than at present (i.e. it was at c. 290 m) (Hodgson and Nairn, 2005 p.504). This supports similarity in the pre and post eruption course of the Tarawera River, at the entry. Allowing a meter for riverbank height, the surface elevation of the Tarawera River entry (and of Lake Tarawera), was 292 MASL ± 1 m on eruption eve. This is further empirical support for our Rotomahana altimetry; given the Kaiwaka Stream connecting the two lakes, descended 12 m (40 ft) from Lake Rotomahana to Lake Tarawera; and an 1858–1886 Lake Rotomahana altimetry of 303 MASL ± 1 –2 m (Bunn & Nolden, 2018).

In 2018, I received advice via traditional landowners of an unreported (c. 2003) gold prospecting borehole at Lake Rotomahana; which returned a silica core sample. At that time, the significance of this was unappreciated, for conventional wisdom held that the Terraces

were lost (pers. comm. Mike Gibbons 7 March, 2018). If this silica sample correlates with our survey mapping of a Terrace, it will be the first empirical evidence from a surviving Terrace. To date, no samples or coordinates from this drilling are available.

Most recently, I assembled further borehole evidence. In the 1960's, a forgotten hydro-electric scheme was planned for the Rotorua lakes. Boreholes were drilled along the Tarawera outlet (one was likely attended by Healy and contributed to our 2017 Rotomahana altimetry). Five more were drilled across the Rotomahana isthmus to assess stability (Nairn, 2002; Paterson, 2003). The White Terrace location is bracketed by three of these boreholes. It lies within 100 m of BH4 and BH5 in Figure 1 (drawn to scale), (Nairn, 2002; Paterson, 2003). Allowing for cartographic, borehole and survey error, a White Terrace overlap with BH4 or BH5 is tenable, and less likely with BH3. Details of the core samples, depth and thickness appear to have been lost when the Ministry of Works was privatised in 1988. As/when we locate surviving coring, a match with Terrace retention sample chemistry and texture would trigger the claim of discovering the White Terrace, not just its location.

Fig. 1: White Terrace survey location bracketed by c. 1970 boreholes (Google Earth™).

Discussion

This first present-day, evidence-based altimetry of the lost Pink and White Terraces, is based on James Healy's 1975 work, 1970 borehole coring from Tarawera River, colonial artwork and to-date sixteen eyewitness reports of the descent of Kaiwaka Stream. Further boreholes were drilled on the Tarawera River entry in 2013 and their cores confirm our altimetry of Lake Rotomahana and Lake Tarawera prior to the 1886 eruption. These findings will help direct future research at Lake Rotomahana, to ideally image, drill and excavate the lost sites of the three fabled Terraces. Resolving the Terrace locations will provide closure for the indigenous Māori who grieve for families killed in the eruptions.

References

Bunn, Rex (2014) Raising the Tattooed Rock- A Tourism Proposal of National Significance, Plenary Meetings of the TTA and PAWTL Project, [Conference Presentation] Rotorua, New Zealand. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32015.25765

Bunn, A. R. and Nolden, S. (2018) “Forensic cartography with Hochstetter’s 1859 Pink and White Terraces survey: Te Otukapuarangi and Te Tarata” *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand*, 48, 39–56. Published online: 7 June 2017.

Bunn R (2020) “Commentary: Locating Relict Sinter Terrace Sites at Lake Rotomahana, New Zealand, With Ferdinand von Hochstetter’s Legacy Cartography, Historic Maps, and LIDAR” *Frontiers in Earth Science* 8:68. DOI: 10.3389/feart.2020.00068

Bunn, A. R. (2021) Submissions to the Māori Affairs Committee, New Zealand House of Representatives, on the Ngāti Rangitihī Claims Settlement Bill, 2021.

<https://www.parliament.nz/en/pb/sc/submissions-and-advice/current?criteria.Keyword=bunn&criteria.Author=M%20Bunn&criteria.DateTo=&parliamentStartDate=2020-11-24&parliamentEndDate=&criteria.DocumentStatus=>

Healy, J. (1975a) “Volcanic Lakes”; in Jolly, V. H., and Brown, J. M. A. (Eds.) *New Zealand Lakes*, Auckland University Press and Oxford University Press, Auckland, 75-79.

Healy, J. (1975b) “Effect of rainfall on Rotorua Lakes” *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand*, 5, 81–83.

Hitchens, C. (2008). *God Is Not Great: How Religion Poisons Everything*. Allen & Unwin. 178.

Hochstetter, F. (1859) *Geology of the province of Auckland, New Zealand* (Delivered to the Members of the Auckland Mechanics’ Institute, June 24, 1859), *New Zealand Government Gazette*, no 23, 14 July 1859.

Hochstetter, F. and Petermann, A. (1864) *Geological and Topographical Atlas of New Zealand: Six Maps of the Provinces of Auckland and Nelson*, Auckland: Delattre.

Hodgson, K. A. and Nairn, I. (2005) “The c. AD 1315 syn-eruption and AD 1904 post-eruption breakout floods from Lake Tarawera, Haroharo caldera, North Island, New Zealand” *New Zealand Journal of Geology and Geophysics*, 48, 491–506.

- Keam R. F. and Lloyd, E. F. (2016) “Post-1886-eruption Rotomahana hot springs” *GOSA Transactions*, 13, 39.
- Keam, R. F. (2016) “The Tarawera eruption, Lake Rotomahana, and the origin of the Pink and White Terraces” *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 314, 10-38.
- Keir, W. (2016) ‘J Healy’s Lake Tarawera Ground Drilling c. 1970’, in Bunn, A. R., *Quest for the Pink and White Terraces*, Bunn, 2016.
- Nairn, I. (2002) *Geology of the Okataina Volcanic Centre*, GNS.156p.
- Paterson, R. (2003) *Lake Rotomahana Outlet Study*, Riley Consultants, Rotorua.
- Smith, S. P. (1887) *The Eruption of Tarawera*, Government Printer, Wellington, 41.
- Smith, S. P. (1894) “Notes on the Present State of the Country Immediately Round the Site of the Eruption of Tarawera” Appendix to the Journals of the House of Representatives, Report for the Year 1893–94. Department of Lands and Survey, 81.
- Reynolds, Q. (1953) *The Amazing Mr Doolittle*. Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Tschirter, C. and White, P. (2014) “Three-dimensional geological model of the greater Lake Tarawera catchment”. *GNS Science*, 2013/155.